

GENDER SENSITIZATION IN TEACHER EDUCATION

Mr. Santhosh Saldanha

Lecturer, SDM College of Education, Ujire.

Email: santhosh.saldanha@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The discrimination is an immoral, behavioral practice of an individual & groups. There are many distinguish areas of discrimination like color, race, caste, ethnicity, nationality, class, religion, sex, language etc. but one of the most challengeable discriminations is based on the gender. There are many issues and challenges created for the female gender. All the challenges faced by women and related gender disparities and inequality are the results of value degradation of the society. Therefore, there is a great need to sensitize the society on gender issues. Gender sensitization is a movement through which the people with stereotype & traditional thinking, should be able to assure equal participation of women and men in decision-making; to facilitate equally; to equally access & the resources; to acquire alike benefits of development; to get equal opportunities in employment ; economic, political, cultural & social sector and also can get equivalent regard in all other aspects of their life and livelihood so that both genders can enjoy their human rights. With the help of education, gender sensitization in educational institutes can create awareness among the children, parents and other members of the community about their roles in future as the men and women. The power of education that can make a great social change. Presently, gender and women studies have become the main subject of study at teacher education. It is also included in the syllabus of teacher education so that pupil teacher can learn how to deal with issues related with gender sensitization. Thus, all the possible concerns should be made by the educational institutions to promote the gender equality in education. our society is rigid, it is difficult to make changes in the mindset of the people. Therefore, Government should introduce welfare schemes for females to make them self-independent. Each educational institutes and school should take initiative to understand the gender-related issues and to sensitize its' concerns staffs, teachers, students and society for the equality. There should be some relevant contents on gender equality in textbooks; a teacher should promote the respect to the girls and women in the classroom environment and outside. Moreover, Government should also introduce

programs and also make ensure the proper implementation of policies and strategies that ensuring the gender equality in the society.

Key Words: Gender sensitization, teacher education.

Introduction

Teacher education is the formal programs that have been established for the preparation of teachers at the elementary- and secondary-school levels. While arrangements of one kind or another for the education of the young have existed at all times and in all societies, it is only recently that schools have emerged as distinctive institutions for this purpose on a mass scale, and teachers as a distinctive occupational category. Gender sensitivity is a human act must be developed among teachers.

Some countries are providing gender sensitivity training, and offer its support to social services and child welfare agencies as well as a number of schools. But, there are no similar initiatives in India currently, but it is imperative that something must be done because education will help trigger change but only when teachers and learners are assisted in adopting classroom initiatives that reflect new images based on a positive gender equity ideology.

According to the mission statement of United Nations Decade of Education for Sustainable Development (ESD) “Teachers are strategically positioned to act as agents of change in order to achieve gender equality, especially through what they teach, how they teach and how they role model their own attitudes, beliefs and practices in the classroom and beyond. Indeed, teachers do not come into classrooms as gender-neutral persons. They are likely to have internalized a patriarchal gender ideology through their upbringing and years of socialization in both formal and informal settings. This paper uses experiential, interactive, participatory and reflective methodologies to sensitize teachers to the classroom practice implications of gender consciousness so that teachers can adopt a gender perspective in their everyday lives and in their teaching functions.”

Strategies for gender sensitization

1. Creating learning environments; Teachers can create the appearance of gender **bias** through nonverbal actions. The first step to correcting this problem is to organize classroom in a way that makes all students feel equal.
2. Establish set of rules; It is important for a teacher to establish a set of rules from the beginning that promote equality. An effective way to do this is to create class rules with students. This permits the teacher to point to the rules as something that the whole class has agreed on. It is important to include

rules that deal with respecting students, respecting the teacher, respecting the gender and participating in class.

3. Classroom seating plan that supports equality. If you find that certain students, regardless of their gender, are not participating in class, try to change your class seating plan. For example, try having students who usually sit in the back come to the front. Teachers tend to interact the most with students sitting closest to them. It is important to change the seating order (if possible) to give all students a chance to sit near the teacher and also make the boys and girls sit together

4. Academic and behavior expectations for equality; Teachers should try to avoid making things easier for either male or female students by giving them easier questions in class, or trying to solve things for the students. Doing this can create the perception that certain students are not as smart as others. Teachers should hold the same expectations of all students.

5. Use group work: Often there will be some students, male or female, who are not comfortable speaking in front of large classes. But, they may feel more comfortable speaking in small groups. In order to give all students the opportunity to take part in class, try doing some activities in small groups of three to four students including both male and female.

Classroom strategies

After organizing your class in a way that promotes equality, the next step is to consider the effects your actions in class.

- Address students equally

One of the main opportunities students have to participate in class is when they are answering teachers' questions. Teachers need to call on or talk to both female and male students in a balanced way. Research shows that both male and female teachers often call on male students to speak in class more often than female students.

- Provide enough time to answer questions.

Some students, male or female, may need time to think about the answer to a question when called on by a teacher. When calling on students who seem to wait longer to answer a question, make sure to give students at least four to five seconds. Research shows that giving students more time to answer will increase the number of students who participate.

- Use gender neutral language

Sometimes in English people use male pronouns when referring to a group. But, this can make female students feel left out. Teachers should use gender neutral pronouns whenever possible. One example is, instead of saying "guys" when referring to a class or group, say "everybody" or "everyone."

- Body language

Teachers may not realize that their body language with female students might be different from what it is with male students. Whenever male or female students are talking, use respectful, listening body language. Face the listener, do not walk away, and do not interrupt students. The teacher can move to different areas of the classroom while speaking. This is important because students sitting far from the teacher tend to participate less.

- Discipline

Be aware when male students insult female students, or female students insult male students.

If the insults appear to be gender-based, students may be discouraged from participating in class in the future. Be quick to intervene and discipline the students making insults. This shows students of either gender that they will be supported. However it is important that both male and female students are given the same discipline for the same actions. These strategies will help teachers create a more equal classroom environment for their students. They will also help teachers effectively manage their classrooms. The best form of teaching is the fair form of teaching!

Ways to promote gender equality in the classroom

1. Be Reflective and be Objective in attitude

First, pay attention to the trends above and do your best to offer more gender-neutral responses to students. You may feel like you already do a good job of this, but it can be difficult to judge your own teaching objectively. It may help to record a video of your classroom in order to take a closer look at your own teaching methods and interactions with students.

2. Get feedback from staff and students

Consider getting feedback from colleagues on any differences they may notice that you don't. Consider getting similar feedback from the students themselves using an anonymous comment box. Consider questions such as: 1. Do you notice any differences in how I treat boys and girls? 2. What do I need to know about you, in terms of gender, to teach you well? 3. Have I made you feel good or bad in regards to your gender at any point? Etc.

3. Use Gender-Neutral Language

One can also change the language within your lessons to help expand students' perspectives beyond gender stereotypes. For example, in assignments one can challenge students' expectations by including a female construction worker or soldier, a male secretary or nurse, and other professions typically associated with a particular gender. When referring to the group as a whole, avoid using gendered terms like 'guys,' which may make female students feel excluded. Instead, use gender-

neutral pronouns like ‘everyone.’ Similarly, one shouldn’t refer to stereotypical characteristics like ‘boys don’t cry’ or ‘girls don’t fight.’ This language lays a foundation that may limit students’ understanding of gender roles.

4. Seat and group students intentionally

It’s common for boys and girls to segregate when choosing friends and seating arrangements. Teachers sometimes encourage this by asking girls and boys to form separate lines in the hallway or even organizing separate sports activities for each group. By creating a dynamic seating chart, you can break up boys- or girls-only cliques and encourage both groups to engage with each other.

5. Use project-based learning

You can also be intentional about integrating of boys and girls within small group projects. The work can be purely academic, with the lessons on gender equity indirect and implicit. By working together, girls and boys can understand the individual behaviors rather than stereotyping ‘girls’ and ‘boys.’ Projects can also be created to explore concepts in and around gender and cultural equity, or to do work in select spaces and communities to nurture the growth of healthy human interdependence.

Conclusion

These strategies aren’t true for every teacher or every group of students, but they are worth considering as you attempt to curb gender biases within your teaching methods. Gender disparity is only one facet of a much larger issue of equity within education. However, by making efforts to break down traditional gender roles in the classroom, you can better prepare students to seek knowledge and participate more fully in discussions and other learning opportunities in many fields, regardless of their gender. The teacher can adopt a number of ways like, setting clear rules to how people should be treated, challenging any negative attitudes, treating all staff and students fairly and equally, creating an all-inclusive culture for staff and students, avoiding stereotypes in examples and resources and using resources with multicultural themes.

References:

1. Dr. Jatinder Kumar Sharma (March 2016). "Understanding the Concept of Sensitisation in Humanities and Social Sciences: An Exploration in Philosophy of Mind". *International Journal of Scientific Research*. **24** (90): 380–400.
2. Aksornkool, Namtip. Joerger, Cindy; Taylor, Elaine (eds.). *Gender sensitivity: a training manual for sensitizing education managers, curriculum and material developers and media professionals to gender concerns*. p. VIII.
3. Bhowmick Soma. "[Gender Sensitization and Police](#)". Retrieved 17 February 2014.
4. Pandey, Ashutosh (2018-07-16). "[Gender Sensitization: Problems and Strategies](#)". *Isaconf*.